

Analysis of a Semitransparent PIFA Element for MIMO Applications

L. Inclan-Sanchez¹

¹ Department of Signal Theory and Communications, Madrid, Spain, linclan@tsc.uc3m.es

Abstract—This paper analyzes the design of a semitransparent Planar Inverted-F Antenna (PIFA) to operate in the 5G band. The proposed antenna consists of a set of metallic wires that form a grid which configures the conductive parts of the antenna. This new radiant element offers an adequate response in terms of gain and impedance matching. On the other hand, it can be easily manufactured using 3D printing techniques. The semitransparent element has been integrated into a 2x2 subarray to analyze its application in MIMO systems. The subarray has been tuned to provide port isolation, good impedance matching, envelope correlation coefficient and radiation characteristics which are desired for MIMO applications. The proposed element offers utility to implement large antennas in array configuration and, at the same time, allows visible light to pass through it.

Index Terms— transparent antenna, PIFA antenna, 3D printing, MIMO system.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the framework of the deployment of new technologies and networks of the so-called fifth generation 5G of communications, new problems arise. More and more antennas are needed for human and machine-type communications, such as in the Internet of Things (IoT). In addition, the current situation includes an increasingly saturated frequency spectrum and the need for the antennas to be integrated observing the environment in which they have to be placed. Therefore, it is necessary to have antenna arrays that allow the development of MIMO systems. But the placement of these large antennas must be compatible with preserving the lighting and visual environment as much as possible.

PIFA antennas are a compact and robust version of patch antennas whose interest for 5G applications has been shown in recent works [1][2][3]. MIMO systems have shown that by using multiple antenna elements in the transmitter and receiver, the channel capacity can be increased without the need to increase the channel bandwidth or transmitted power level [2]. One of the problems that these systems have is that they require large dimensions for their implementation and it is very often difficult to have useful surfaces large enough for their deployment. Therefore, this study explores the possibility of designing compact antennas that allow light to pass through and offering good performance for MIMO applications.

In recent years, two options for designing transparent antennas have been considered [4][5][6]. First, there is the

possibility of using transparent materials to implement the antennas. This needs the use of transparent dielectric materials and also transparent conductive materials. Transparent dielectric materials offer a very good level of optical transmission and, although they present losses, is not a problem below the 10GHz frequency range. Quite different is what happens with transparent conductive materials. For example, thin sheets of doped plastic material with conductive particles that are frequently used have a high level of losses [7]. The antennas that have been designed with these conductive sheets offer low efficiencies. Secondly, a well-known strategy has recently aroused great interest. I refer to the design of antennas with metallic grids. This solution reproduces the behavior of the metallic parts of the antenna through the use of conductive wires. This means that the wires are grouped in a metallic grid that form, from the electrical point of view, the conductive surfaces necessary for the design of the antennas. In the work proposed in this paper, this second possibility is chosen to analyze compact antennas with low visual impact. These antennas can be integrated into electronic devices that require lighting such as solar cells [5]. They could also be used to implement larger antennas, such as an array, allowing the passage of most of the natural light. Therefore, they could be used in windows of buildings or in windshields of vehicles. Finally, the study puts the emphasis on exploring low-cost and simple designs that can be manufactured using 3D printing techniques.

Fig. 1. Simplified scheme of the main parameters of the PIFA antenna.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

In the following, the conceptual procedure followed for the antenna design will be detailed. All numerical analysis have been performed with the commercial simulator CST Microwave Studio.

A. Semitransparente element description

A PIFA is a type of patch antenna of size smaller than usual, as its approximate dimension is of the order of $\lambda/4$, where λ is the wavelength in the substrate. In our case, given that the objective is transparency, it is proposed to design the antenna without a substrate. This is possible thanks to the fact that the antenna will be manufactured using 3D printing, which makes it possible to print at the same time the support structures that hold the grid of the PIFA metallization. As a consequence, the antenna reduces its complexity, the ohmic losses due to the dielectric and also its cost. Obviously when defining the cavity associated with the PIFA on air permittivity, the result is a larger physical size to obtain the resonant length. The center of the future 5G band in Europe, comprising the frequencies between 3.4 GHz and 3.8GHz, is considered as the target frequency for the antenna. A schematic of the proposed antenna with the relevant geometric parameters can be seen in Fig.1.

Fig. 2. Models used for the numerical analysis of the PIFA antenna. With conductor (top) and with metallic grid (down) as ground plane.

To analyze the behavior of the proposed antenna, simulations will be performed using the two models that are shown in Fig.2. The models include the metallization of the PIFA patch formed by a grid of three and six wires in the transverse and longitudinal dimensions respectively as shown in figures Fig.1 and Fig.2. On the other hand, the ground plane of the antenna is composed of a square grid of seven by seven wires, as shown in Fig. 2. The behavior of the PIFA with the metallic grid with a homogeneous conductor ground plane will be studied as a first step as

shown in Fig. 2. The conductivity of all metal parts in this first part of the work will be considered as $\sigma=5e7$ S/m. The initial dimensions for the antenna include the following fixed parameters: $w_p=10$ mm for the PIFA patch width and $h=3$ mm for the patch metallization height above the ground plane. On the other hand the width of the wires is $d=0.8$ mm, and the thickness of the wires is $t=1$ mm. The period or separation of the wires in the grid will depend in each case on the dimensions of the ground plane. The real part of the simulated impedance for the antenna is displayed in Fig. 3, for different sizes of the ground plane and for two cases (with grid and with PEC). The figure shows the result obtained for the antenna with $l_p=16.3$ mm for the case with grid as ground plane and with $l_p=16.7$ mm for the case with conductor as ground plane. The antenna response is more sensitive to the size of the ground plane for the case with grid. There are three objectives identified when choosing the grid topology; ensure the grid's electrical homogeneity, to verify that the antenna obtains an adequate level of gain, and to avoid the increase in back radiation produced by non-continuous ground plane. Simulations have been carried out to evaluate the front to back ratio for different sizes of the ground plane. It can be seen in Fig. 4 how the dimensions of $m_x = 40$ mm and $m_x = 50$ mm have the highest front to back ratio. In addition to increasing the ground plane, the antenna has a greater contribution to its radiant surface and a greater gain as Fig. 5 shows. However, as the number of wires in the grid remains constant, their separation increases, which consequently increases the level of back radiation of the antenna as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Real part of the antenna input impedance over frequency.

Fig. 4. Simulated front to back ratio varying the dimension of the grid in the ground plane.

Fig. 5. Calculated gain for the grid PIFA for different values of $m_x = m_y$.

A trade off between gain and back radiation is then necessary. Considering a compact design a priority, $m_x = m_y = 40$ mm is selected as the size for the ground plane. The longitudinal dimension of the antenna and the feeding point are optimized to center the antenna response at a frequency of $f = 3.6$ GHz. The parameters obtained for the antenna with grid after this process are $l_p = 16.7$ mm and $o_f = 11.2$ mm. In this case the separation between wires in the grid is 6.53 mm for the ground plane and 3.1 mm for the metallization of the PIFA patch (in the longitudinal dimension).

B. Antenna behavior and design parameters

This section shows some results of the performance achieved by the PIFA. First, the ratio between the surface occupied by the wires, both the patch and the ground plane, with the entire surface of the antenna has been calculated. Consequently, a level of transparency for the proposed PIFA antenna between 65% and 70% has been estimated depending on the width of the wires and the size considered for the patch. Secondly, the PIFA radiation patterns for the two ground plane cases have been simulated. The same behavior as the antenna with the continuous ground plane is observed for the PIFA with the grid as ground plane. Fig. 6 shows the comparison between the return losses for the grid design at the central frequency and those obtained for the case with the conductor as ground plane. In this second case, it can be seen in the figure how to obtain the impedance matching at $f = 3.6$ GHz requires a slightly larger size for the PIFA.

Fig. 6. Simulated reflection coefficient for individual element with two thicknesses (h) in the antenna cavity.

Through the analysis of the simulated Ez field distributions for the PIFA, it has been possible to compare the behavior of the antenna with metallic grid with the case of continuous ground plane. A similar behavior has been observed in both cases, which proves that the semitransparent structure correctly performs its electrical function.

C. Manufacturing with 3D printing techniques

In this section a relevant aspect related to the feasibility of the proposed solution is discussed. The manufacture of the designed antenna implies metallizing both the PIFA grid and the ground plane, there existing two options. The first is printing directly with conductive filament. This solution is still somewhat distant because the conductivity of these materials is still two or three orders of magnitude below what is necessary. The second possibility is to print first with dielectric material and then proceed to metallize these parts. As proof of concept we are painting the material with silver paint, whose content of silver particles is 50% and therefore according to the manufacturer its real conductivity is of the order of 1/10 to 1/100 that of copper. To estimate the gain that we can have for the antenna with this procedure, the PIFA response has been simulated with some lower conductivity values. The simulated results obtained for the PIFA realized gain (with grid ground plane) with the initial conductivity and with a second value of $\sigma = 5e5$ S/m are shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Realized gain for the PIFA for two conductivity values.

D. Antenna bandwidth

One of the limitations that PIFA antenna can suffer is a reduced operating bandwidth. In order to appreciate the attainable bandwidth, some adjustments have been made in the antenna to improve it. The PIFA is a small-size patch, therefore by increasing the thickness of the antenna cavity we can reduce its quality factor. In our case, we have implemented this procedure by increasing the distance between the antenna patch and the ground plane with grid up to $h = 4$ mm as shown in Fig. 8. In this figure, S_{11} parameters for the initial PIFA and for the new response centered at $f = 3.6$ GHz with height $h = 4$ mm are shown. The geometric parameters of the antenna have had to be adjusted again, resulting the values: $l_p = 17$ mm and $o_f = 9$ mm. The PIFA with this modification achieves a bandwidth of 7% which allows to cover most of the 5G frequency band in Europe. Finally, the realized gain obtained for the last PIFA

antenna design with greater bandwidth compared to the initial case is evaluated. It has been observed that the gain in this case is very similar to the previous and always above values of 3dB, reaching the peak value of 3.9 dB at $f=3.65$ GHz. In any case, these values are in the range of usual values for a PIFA.

Fig. 8. Simplified scheme of the main parameters of the PIFA antenna.

III. 4-PORTS SUBARRAY PERFORMANCE

This section integrates the semitransparent PIFA element into a 2x2 subarray. The ultimate goal is to design a larger array that allows massive MIMO systems to be deployed with low visual impact on large surfaces of architectural structures such as building windows.

A. Subarray configuration

Different possibilities for the configuration of the subarray have been systematically evaluated. The case shown here has a ground plane size of $m_x = m_y = 40$ mm for the individual element which is the same as that analyzed in the previous sections. Finally a 2x2 subarray of dimensions $0.48\lambda \times 0.48\lambda$ where λ is free space wavelength at 3.6 GHz is proposed as Fig. 9 shows.

Fig. 9. Proposed 2x2 subarray of semitransparent PIFA elements.

The Fig. 9 shows the final configuration of the antennas, the PIFAS are successively rotated ninety degrees to achieve two effects. The first is to avoid that two adjacent elements are coupled in the E-plane of the antenna. Second, because individual elements are linearly polarized their rotation increases polarization decoupling.

B. Mutual coupling

A well-known property is that MIMO systems performance improves with lower correlation between the signals on different antennas [2]. In our case, this distance is close to half a wavelength, so the initial coupling level is limited. Coupling has been simulated using full wave models. The Fig. 11 shows in red line the S- parameters of the most representative direct couplings for the proposed design. The proposed subarray in this case has a continuous ground plane to the four radiating elements, this ground plane that is shared by all antennas produces an increase in coupling due to the propagation of surface waves. The coupling level obtained in this case is close to -15dB for the S21 and S31 that correspond to the adjacent elements. While for the element located on the diagonal the coupling, S41, reaches a level of approximately -25 dB.

Fig. 10. Front view of the proposed subarray with the notation of non metallized grid parts as decoupling technique.

Fig. 11. S- parameters for the subarray with continuous metallized ground plane (red lines) and for the proposed with decoupling technique (blue lines). The lines correspond to: S21 solid, S31 dashed and S41 dashdotted.

In our design in which the ground plane is manufactured by 3D printing that has to be metallized later. An interesting possibility due to its simplicity is not to metallize the part of the ground plane between elements. In this way, the electrical continuity of the metallic surface made with the grid would be avoided. This is a useful and well known technique in patch design, which has been widely used with good results. To analyze the application of this coupling reduction technique, couplings have been simulated in the case where the parts marked in red in Fig. 10 are not metallic. This produces a truncation in the metallic layer that

supports the surface waves. The couplings levels obtained for the most significant ports can be seen in Fig. 11 (blue color). For the coupling between adjacent elements a reduction of 5 dB is observed, reaching levels of approximately -20dB for the S21 and S31. While in the case of coupling with the element located on the diagonal, the level falls below -30dB for the entire band of interest. By means of simulations it has been possible to verify how the lack of electrical continuity in the ground plane allows to reduce coupling levels below -20dB between all ports, which validates the interest of using these elements in the implementation of high isolation antenna arrays.

C. MIMO performance

The envelope correlation coefficient (ECC) is a useful measure to evaluate the diversity performance of a MIMO antenna. The theoretically estimate of ECC is ideally calculated from 3-D radiation pattern of the element. In our case we assume that the MIMO antenna will operate in a uniform multipath rich environment. In this case it can be alternatively calculated by using the scattering parameters simulated from CST. The computed ECC for the proposed MIMO system is below 0.05 for the desired band, which ensures a good diversity performance.

The elevation plane view of simulated far field radiation patterns of the MIMO antennas at 3.6GHz is shown in Fig. 12. Due to the symmetrical nature of the antenna, the simulated radiation patterns show close similarity. That is, they are identical two by two since the subarray has a rotational symmetry. The position of the antennas increases the orthogonality between polarizations and a lower level of correlation between the radiation patterns. In our case, the individual element proposed is not very directive, for this reason it is necessary to analyze the global effects on the diversity gain of the system.

Fig. 12. Simulated radiation patterns at 3.6 GHz (XZ plane) for the four excitation ports in the subarray.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has described the design of a new semitransparent low-cost PIFA antenna. The antenna is designed to be easily manufactured with 3D printing techniques. The patch of the antenna and its ground plane is

implemented by a metallic grid achieving a transparency of approximately 65%. Good impedance bandwidths at 3.6GHz have been obtained for two configurations (with respectively 5.5% and 7% bandwidth). The individual element gain is close to 4.5dB. The semitransparent element has been integrated into a 2x2 subarray. The subarray has been designed to provide port isolation, good impedance matching, and radiation characteristics to improve diversity. Finally, a decoupling technique based on non-metallized grid between antenna elements has been proposed to enhance port-to-port isolation. The proposed antenna can be used in 5G future MIMO applications for locations where optical transparency is necessary.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the Spanish Government under project PID2019-107688RB-C21.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Lin, K. Saito, M. Takahashi and K. Ito, "A Compact Planar Inverted-F Antenna for 2.45 GHz On-Body Communications," in IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 60, no. 9, pp. 4422-4426, Sept. 2012.
- [2] M. V. Komandla, G. Mishra and S. K. Sharma, "Investigations on Dual Slant Polarized Cavity-Backed Massive MIMO Antenna Panel With Beamforming," in IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 6794-6799, Dec. 2017
- [3] D. Q. Liu, M. Zhang, H. J. Luo, H. L. Wen and J. Wang, "Dual-Band Platform-Free PIFA for 5G MIMO Application of Mobile Devices," in IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 66, no. 11, pp. 6328-6333, Nov. 2018.
- [4] S. Hong, Y. Kim and C. Won Jung, "Transparent Microstrip Patch Antennas With Multilayer and Metal-Mesh Films," in IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, vol. 16, pp. 772-775, 2017.
- [5] S. K. Podilchak, D. Comite, B. K. Montgomery, Y. Li, V. Gomez-Guillamon Buendia and Y. M. M. Antar, "Solar-Panel Integrated Circularly Polarized Meshed Patch for Cubesats and Other Small Satellites," in IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 96560-96566, 2019
- [6] Q. L. Li, S. W. Cheung, D. Wu and T. I. Yuk, "Optically Transparent Dual-Band MIMO Antenna Using Micro-Metal Mesh Conductive Film for WLAN System," in IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters, vol. 16, pp. 920-923, 2017.
- [7] M. E. Zamudio and M. Behzadirad and C. Christodoulou and T. Busani, "Optimization of AZO films for integrating optically transparent antennas with photovoltaics," in Applied Physics Letters, vol. 110, no. 23, 234101, 2017.